

Open source software and workflows

A driving force for innovation in life sciences

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Key terms

Open source software

Software with source code available to the public to inspect, modify, enhance and redistribute, according to the chosen license. More precisely, this concept is referred to as 'free and open source software'¹ (FOSS).

Workflows

In this report, 'workflow' refers to a computational workflow – a special kind of software expressed in a specific language targeted at handling multi-step, multi-code data pipelines, data analyses and other data-handling operations, especially through the efficient use of computational resources to transform data inputs into desired outputs. Workflows increasingly incorporate machine learning models and are critical for integrating and deploying software code and data analysis².

Workflow management systems

Specialised software systems that help scientists design, manage, execute and partially or fully automate their computational workflows from start to finish.

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Free_and_open-source_software

² Wilkinson, S.R., Alohalla, M., Belhajjame, K. et al. Applying the FAIR Principles to computational workflows. *Sci Data* 12, 328 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-04451-9>

Open source software tools and workflows to support innovation

Large, complex datasets are fundamental to life science research, and extracting meaningful insights from them is essential for developing new products and services. This requires robust analytical workflows and sustainably maintained, professional-grade software. These tools enable data aggregation, analysis and infrastructure support, while promoting reproducibility, portability, trust and productivity, often in alignment with FAIR principles^{2,3}. While open source software (OSS) has been an important pillar for research and development for decades, the increasing ubiquity of machine learning (ML) has further emphasised the importance of workflows, as manual tasks increasingly shift towards to algorithm-driven processes^{4,5}.

Life scientists in industry and academia use open source software and workflows (OSSW) to build analytical pipelines tailored to specific research purposes, including clinical studies and the development of diagnostic or therapeutic applications. In turn, these scientists often contribute expertise to design, validate and enrich open workflows, fostering a community of practice and a wealth of open knowledge with diverse applications and methodologies. Such collective efforts produce invaluable assets for research across industry and academia.

Investigating current practices in OSSW is crucial for understanding trends and developing best practices for sharing and using open software and workflows. In this report, we conducted a qualitative analysis based on 15 interviews with the representatives from bioinformatics companies, alongside a quantitative analysis of empirical data collected from GitHub and the Galaxy platform. The findings underscore the importance of OSSW in driving innovation, fostering collaboration and enhancing transparency in research.

3 FAIR Research Software Principles (https://eiverse.software/RSQKit/fair_rs), Research Software Quality Kit (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14892767>)

4 Baird, A., & Maruping, L. M. (2021). The next generation of research on IS use: A theoretical framework of delegation to and from agentic IS artifacts. *MIS quarterly*, 45(1). <https://doi.org/10.25300/MISQ/2021/15882>

5 Stelmaszak, M., Möhlmann, M., & Sørensen, C. (2024). When algorithms delegate to humans: Exploring human-algorithm interaction at Uber. *MIS quarterly*, 49 (1). <https://doi.org/10.25300/MISQ/2024/17911>

How open source tools support bioinformatics companies

OSS plays a crucial role in research across academia and industry. Over the past decade, OSS has transformed industries such as bioinformatics, biotechnology⁶ and pharmaceuticals⁷ by increasing reliance on professionals skilled in software engineering, research data management and AI, giving rise to so-called 'invert firms'⁸. In these firms, employees not only bring technical expertise but also equip companies with open tools and workflows that accelerate product and service innovation. Many organisations now strategically build their business and operational models around open source, while others contribute to and use them extensively⁹. As with open data initiatives, OSS has played an important role in enhancing openness and transparency,¹⁰ and in shaping new companies in the bioinformatics domain¹¹.

Advanced computational analysis – particularly involving ML – has become critical in life science product and service development¹². Workflows encode algorithmic approaches to load and transform data, train, test, package and deploy ML models. Also, they facilitate the monitoring and governance of ML models, enhancing reproducibility and trust^{13,14}. As the role of ML becomes more pivotal¹⁵, these workflows are becoming a key part of OSSW.

“ Open source code, workflows and software – developed and maintained by the global community – play a crucial role in highly specialised, innovation-driven fields like drug discovery and development.” – Interviewee, Ardigen

“ Open source tools and public databases, being state of the art and widely validated by the scientific community, facilitate rapid advancements in research with minimal costs, particularly in the field of drug discovery.” – Interviewee, Knowing01s

“ For a resource-constrained startup, adopting standardised tools and workflows allows us to focus on our value proposition, rather than diverting resources to baseplate code and infrastructure. By integrating open source tools, which benefit from continuous community support and evolution, we can significantly reduce development overhead and accelerate our time to market.” – Interviewee, Cambrium

6 Vassilakopoulou, P., Skorge, E., & Aanestad, M. (2019). Enabling openness of valuable information resources: Curbing data subtractability and exclusion. *Information Systems Journal*, 29(4), 768–786. <https://doi.org/10.1111/isj.12191>

7 Priego, L. P., & Wareham, J. (2024). Data Commoning in the Life Sciences. *MIS Quarterly*, 48(2). <https://doi.org/10.25300/MISQ/2023/17439>

8 Parker, G., Van Alstyne, M., & Jiang, X. (2017). Platform ecosystems. *MIS Quarterly*, 41(1), 255–266. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2861574>

9 Shaikh, M., & Vaast, E. (2016). Folding and unfolding: Balancing openness and transparency in open source communities. *Information Systems Research*, 27(4), 813–833. <https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.2016.0646>

10 Lifshitz-Assaf, H. (2018). Dismantling knowledge boundaries at NASA: The critical role of professional identity in open innovation. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 63(4), 746–782. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0001839217747876>

11 Rothe, H., Lauer, K. B., Talbot-Cooper, C., & Sivizaca Conde, D. J. (2023). Digital entrepreneurship from cellular data: How omics afford the emergence of a new wave of digital ventures in health. *Electronic Markets*, 33(1), 48. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12525-023-00669-w>

12 Lou, B., & Wu, L. (2021). AI on Drugs: Can Artificial Intelligence Accelerate Drug Development? Evidence from a Large-Scale Examination of Bio-Pharma Firms. *Management Information Systems Quarterly*, 45(3), 1451–1482. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3524985>

13 Sculley, D., Holt, G., Golovin, D., et al. (2015). Hidden technical debt in machine learning systems. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 28. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/2969442.2969519>

14 Walsh, I., Fishman, D., Garcia-Gasulla, D., et al. (2021). DOME: recommendations for supervised machine learning validation in biology. *Nature Methods*, 18(10), 1122–1127. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-021-01205-4>

15 Xu, Y., Liu, X., Cao, X., et al. (2021). Artificial intelligence: A powerful paradigm for scientific research. *The Innovation*, 2(4). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xinn.2021.100179>

Why companies are turning to open source software and workflows

Productivity through cost reduction

Open source tools boost productivity by providing code at little or no cost. Developers benefit from the collective expertise of global communities, and access to OSSW significantly improves the efficiency of private code development^{16,17} by reducing development time and expense – ultimately driving product improvements or service quality.

“ OSS enhances innovation by enabling the company to build on existing tools, thereby reducing development time. Also, exposure to open source tools fosters skill development.” — Interviewee, SeQone

Trust and credibility

Legitimacy is critical in life sciences, due to stringent regulatory requirements and significant risks associated with many applications. By adopting OSS, companies can foster trust through the use of community-vetted OSSW. This approach not only showcases their capacity to develop high-quality code in an open environment, but also enhances credibility by aligning with prominent research institutions¹⁸.

“ Community-vetted tools offer reliability, as bugs are often caught and fixed by a broader user base.” — Interviewee, Cambrium

Productivity through community engagement

Adopting open source code allows developers to tap into the insights and feedback of a broad, diverse community. Developers can use reported OSSW issues or limitations to refine and validate their solutions¹⁹. This collaborative environment not only drives innovation, but also accelerates the overall improvement and reliability of software, often leading to the discovery of novel approaches²⁰.

“ Building a community of experts dedicated to contributing to open source tools demands significant commitment. In return, transparency builds trust and the company gains recognition from the community for its research expertise, fostering commercial partnerships.” — Interviewee, Helical AI

16 Eilhard, J., & Ménière, Y. (2009). A look inside the forge: Developer productivity and spillovers in open source projects. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 1316772; <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1316772>

17 Perez-Riverol, Y., Bittremieux, W., Noble, W. S., et al. (2025). Open-Source and FAIR Research Software for Proteomics. *Journal of Proteome Research*, 24(5), 2222-2234. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jproteome.4c01079>

18 Marsan, J., Carillo, K. D. A., & Negoita, B. (2020). Entrepreneurial actions and the legitimation of free/open source software services. *Journal of Information Technology*, 35(2), 143–160. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0268396219886879>

19 Faraj, S., von Krogh, G., Monteiro, E., & Lakhani, K. R. (2016). Special section introduction – Online community as space for knowledge flows. *Information Systems Research*, 27(4), 668–684. <https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.2016.0682>

20 Fürstenau, D., Baiyere, A., Schewina, K., Schulte-Althoff, M., & Rothe, H. (2023). Extended generativity theory on digital platforms. *Information Systems Research*, 34(4), 1686–1710. <https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.2023.1209>

Customer acquisition and visibility

When companies contribute to OSSW, they engage directly with established communities on platforms like GitHub or Galaxy. This proactive participation increases their reach and connects them with prospective users and clients⁹.

“ The company uses open source tools and data when relevant because they are well documented and peer reviewed, and this helps the company build credibility with clients, especially in the academic world, where transparency is valued.” — Interviewee, Saphetor

Transparency

Open workflows provide full transparency in how code, data and ML models are handled and executed. These benefits extend to software testing and quality assurance, ensuring consistency throughout the software development cycle. With computational approaches and ML increasingly permeating life sciences, the ability to monitor and control data and models is increasingly critical. Public tracking, community discussions and collaborative maintenance of workflow changes further strengthen reproducibility. Sharing and version tracking workflows openly or among communities via registries such as WorkflowHub promotes transparent reuse and reliability of published results²¹.

“ Integrating ML models into the same open framework makes them highly interchangeable; reusable workflows reduce redundant coding.” — Interviewee, Helical AI

“ Using open source tools like Nextflow and nf-core allows organisations to run best-practice pipelines off the shelf, which are reproducible and can be executed on various infrastructures.” — Interviewee, Seqera

Mission-driven goals

OSS has long been associated with democratisation, enabling broad audiences, including under-resourced groups and small businesses to use, share, modify and contribute to high-quality software²². For some companies, engagement with OSS is not just a technical choice, but a commitment to broader societal impact. By embedding their mission and values into code or licensing agreements, these organisations help shape the future of products and services²³.

“ Employees are motivated by the company’s mission to enable open science and open source development, and enjoy working in an environment that values transparency and community contribution.” — Anonymous

21 Gustafsson, O.J.R., Wilkinson, S.R., Bacall, F. et al. WorkflowHub: a registry for computational workflows. *Sci Data* 12, 837 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-04786-3>

22 Allen, J. P. (2012). Democratizing business software: Small business ecosystems for open source applications. *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, 30(1), 28. <https://doi.org/10.17705/1CAIS.03028>

23 Lindberg, A., Berente, N., Howison, J., & Lyytinen, K. (2024). Discursive Modulation in Open Source Software: How Online Communities Shape Novelty and Complexity. *Management Information Systems Quarterly*, 48(4), 1395–1422. <https://doi.org/10.25300/MISQ/2023/16872>

Strategic approaches to open source software and workflows in industry

The interviews revealed three ways companies in the life science sector engage with OSSW.

It is important to recognise that a company's portfolio may include products and services aligned with different OSSW engagement strategies.

Different approaches to Open Source Software and Workflows (OSSW)

Open source first

Companies adopting an open source first approach integrate OSSW as the foundation of their business strategy. They actively develop and contribute to open source projects, often deriving revenue by providing additional specialised services, consulting or tailored client support. These organisations invest substantially in advancing the open source ecosystem, actively contributing to the OSSW community. Their primary motivation is to establish trust with customers and the wider research community – users who adopt their open source tools often turn to them for expertise. Additionally, they perceive their open source commitments both as giving back to the community and as a direct or indirect source of revenue.

For example, **Seqera** provides an end-to-end licensed platform built on the open source workflow manager

Nextflow²⁴ and supports community-driven nf-core pipelines. Both Nextflow and nf-core are continuously improved by community contributors, as well as Seqera. While certain platform-specific code remains proprietary to enable commercial products, these licensed solutions help fund stewardship of the open source projects. Even though custom requests may occasionally lead to divergence from the core open source project, Seqera's approach exemplifies how open source can serve a sustainable and successful business model.

Companies adopting this open source first model demonstrate that community-driven innovation is a pathway to competitive advantage.

²⁴ Nextflow is an open source specialised software system that helps scientists design, manage and execute their computational workflows in a reproducible way. Due to its scalability and reproducibility characteristics it is used by several companies, in addition to academic research.

Open source support

Companies integrate open source components into their products and services without fully opening their core offerings. They use open source to enhance and extend solutions while keeping key innovations proprietary, striking a balance between collaboration and competitive advantage. Unlike open source first companies, these organisations do not explicitly align their business strategies with open source software in their public positioning. This approach provides the flexibility to adapt, disinvest or replace open source components with proprietary alternatives, or gradually adopt a more open source-oriented model.

For example, **Ardigen**, an AI-driven contract research organisation for drug discovery, leverages open source tools such as Nextflow and actively contributes to the nf-core community. It uses a mix of private and public repositories, depending on project needs. Openly sharing workflows builds trust and demonstrates their R&D capability. However, proprietary algorithms and regulated software remain private to ensure security, compliance and intellectual property (IP) protection. Balancing openness with proprietary advantages and sensitive data protection is a significant challenge, further complicated by IP conflicts and licensing requirements.

By strategically adopting open source support models, companies unlock significant benefits such as efficiency, interoperability and stronger credibility with clients and technology partners.

Open source ingestion

Companies that follow the open source ingestion approach rely on proprietary software and platforms to deliver value as part of their core products and services. While they might use open source libraries and tools, this is often seen as a way to enhance their functionality or leverage existing solutions without open sourcing their core products. Their strategic advantage lies in their unique, closed-source offerings and the specialised features they deliver through seamless integration.

For instance, **Cambrium** focuses on molecular design technology, leveraging ML to develop sustainable biomaterials. It integrates open source tools for proprietary data analysis and relies on platforms like Nextflow for workflow orchestration and reproducibility. Most workflows are proprietary, tailored to Cambrium's infrastructure and fine-tuned with proprietary data, reflecting investor concerns about IP protection. Occasionally, non-core software is shared through academic collaborations to foster reproducibility of workflows and innovation, which also helps attract talent and reduce redundant development efforts.

Maintaining open source projects demands resources that many ventures lack; dependence on external workflows and software also introduces risk that require management, such as licensing changes, compatibility issues.

Example strategies from four interviewed companies

Appsilon

Appsilon is a software development and consulting company founded in 2013 specialising in advanced data analytics, data visualisation and custom ML solutions. As a small enterprise, it alternates between open source first and open source ingestion strategies. By making much of its code publicly available, Appsilon builds credibility, attracts clients and contributes back to the community its software originates from. The company also monitors public adoption of these tools to determine if new developments benefit the wider community. Their open source tools can reduce manual work, leading to automation and decreasing the cost of processes like FDA submission due to the lack of license fees.

However, Appsilon does not disclose proprietary workflows developed for pharmaceutical clients. Core frameworks and workflows remain closed-source to retain a competitive commercial edge. The use of external workflows has also presented challenges, particularly around scalability and license compatibility when integrating them with proprietary client solutions.

Saphetor

Saphetor was founded in 2014 and provides software as a service platform with proprietary algorithms to automate variant classification across genomic data sources and publications. As a medium-sized enterprise, the company strategically combines open source first and open source ingestion strategies.

The platform integrates open science data and provides a free tool for searching variants in open datasets, though the underlying code remains closed. The paid version offers access to proprietary databases – a necessity because the company cannot afford expensive licenses while offering data or algorithms for free. Maintaining open source projects and fostering community engagement incurs costs, so revenue generation is essential. Saphetor uses open source tools and data when relevant because they are well-documented and peer-reviewed. This approach builds trust and credibility with clients, particularly in academia where transparency is highly valued. Saphetor thus strikes a balance between advancing open science and sustaining its business model.

Intelliseq

Intelliseq was founded in 2014 and provides a cloud-based platform for the automated analysis and interpretation of human genomic sequence variations. As a small enterprise, it has shifted its approach from open source support to open source ingestion. The company uses open source analytical software, and initially released some tools as open code. However, investor concerns and competitive pressures prompted a transition to private repositories to protect IP.

Intelliseq values open science and open source tools, recognising their importance for community-driven development and as a vital resource for training bioinformaticians. However, stringent data security and privacy requirements in medical genomics pose significant challenges to open source adoption. Additionally, integrating open source workflows can be complex due to differences in programming languages, standards and platforms, often requiring extensive adaptation or even complete recreation.

PacBio

PacBio, a large enterprise established in 2004, specialises in the development and manufacture of gene sequencing systems, including instruments, reagents and analytical software. While not primarily a software company, it actively supports open source initiatives combining open source support and open source ingestion strategies. PacBio provides analytical software through a combination of proprietary and open source code, often free of charge, to encourage adoption of its sequencing technology by making data analysis more accessible. By sharing its workflows, PacBio leverages community expertise to enhance tool development and foster collaboration. This approach also increases the visibility of PacBio's research within the scientific community.

Ensuring consistent and proper attribution of open source tools in both academic and commercial contexts remains a challenge. To safeguard against hacking and the use of unauthorised third-party products, PacBio maintains proprietary code for the core instrument control software.

How companies integrate impact metrics with open source software and workflows

To understand how OSS and collaborative workflows shape real-world innovation, we interviewed decision-makers from 15 life-science companies (three large, four mid-sized and eight small companies; see *Methods* section for details) and examined their OSSW activities on GitHub. One of the most notable ways individuals and organisations demonstrate their commitment to OSSW is through active participation on platforms such as GitHub – where software is developed openly, iterated collectively and made accessible to the wider community. Analysing the GitHub activity of these companies allowed us to see how they adopt and implement open source in practice.

Visibility versus active contribution

Large companies often attract significant attention for their open source projects, reflected in higher star and fork counts on GitHub – indicators of popularity and, possibly, broad adoption. However, their level of active collaboration and direct contribution rates are typically lower.

In contrast, mid-sized and small companies receive less visibility, but show higher developer engagement, marked by more frequent commits, larger contributor pools and higher contribution intensity per project.

“Public adoption (GitHub stars, forks, conference mentions) signals quality and establishes validation.” — Interviewee, Appilon

“Researchers do not always ‘star’ repositories, indicating the problem of this type of popularity assessment for open repositories.” — Anonymous

Company & repository distribution by company type

Large companies

Mid companies

Small companies

Distribution of the 15 interviewed companies by size (small, mid, large) and each group's share of publicly-available GitHub repositories, retrieved via the GitHub API.

Repository metrics by company type

Four-panel figure comparing repository metrics by company size, based on 15 interviewed companies.

Global community collaboration and contributions

The development and maintenance of OSSW relies on a global community. Our interviewees, drawn from eight different countries, maintain OSSW on GitHub that receives worldwide contributions. This underscores the importance of decentralised cooperation, openness, and strong communication across geographically dispersed teams.

Worldwide collaboration

The data reveals a diverse contributor base across companies of all sizes: repositories from large companies attracted contributors from 26 countries, mid-sized companies from 59 countries, and small companies from 38 countries. These findings highlight the broad appeal and collaborative nature of open source, regardless of organisational scale.

Dissemination and community building in open source projects is important – simply making code available does not guarantee its adoption.” — Interviewee, large data analytics company

Galaxy's global reach across life science domains

The Galaxy platform is a cornerstone of bioinformatics and life science data analysis, providing a collaborative space to execute, develop and disseminate workflows and software tools²⁵. Behind this diverse platform of tools lies an intricate web of sharing patterns, contributor behaviour and evolving tool maintenance practices, all essential for understanding how knowledge and technology propagate across the platform. While Galaxy's primary focus is life sciences, its global distribution – supported by a network of OSSW repositories on GitHub – offers a clear overview of the diversity of tools used in this domain.

To shed light on how workflows and tools are shared within Galaxy, we analysed the platform's ecosystem, identifying the key trends and behaviours that define its community-driven model. The basis of this analysis is a curated dataset of around 6800 Galaxy ToolShed repositories²⁶ owned by 636 distinct ToolShed owners. In

Galaxy, each tool is typically developed and maintained in a dedicated repository, mapped into 15 distinct primary domains. Because many tools span multiple research domains, we used a weighted distribution (rather than simple headcounts) to identify the most prominent domains²⁷.

Key insight

Galaxy is not merely a collection of isolated tools; it is a dynamic, interconnected ecosystem where tools are frequently integrated across diverse life sciences subdomains. This integration drives collaboration and cross-functional reuse in ways that simple metrics cannot fully capture.

Weighted distribution of Galaxy tools by category

25 The Galaxy Community. The Galaxy platform for accessible, reproducible, and collaborative data analyses: 2024 update, *Nucleic Acids Research*, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkac410>

26 This dataset includes all publicly-available repositories from the Galaxy ToolShed as of 26 February 2025, retrieved via the ToolShed API.

27 The weights correspond to the probabilities generated by the topic model, where each probability indicates the likelihood that a repository belongs to a specific category.

To assess the impact of Galaxy's most popular tools, we analysed the top 50 most-downloaded tools and their primary categories. Each tool was assigned to its primary category based on the highest weight, giving a clear perspective on where each tool predominantly belongs²⁸. The analysis revealed a classic long-tail distribution observed in other platform ecosystems, where some 'superstar' workflows are complemented by a long tail of other workflows with low to moderate levels of use.

The most downloaded tools that belong in diverse categories showcase how Galaxy supports a wide

range of scientific needs. The most frequently downloaded repositories belong to categories such as Workflow Automation & Meta-tools, Formatting & Conversion and Genomic & Variant Analysis. Standout tools – including *FastQC* (Genomic & Variant Analysis), *data_manager_manual* (Workflow Automation) and *collection_column_join* (Data Integration & Merging) – have become indispensable in many research pipelines. Their widespread adoption highlights the Galaxy community's emphasis on reliability, automation and effective data management.

Top 50 most downloaded tools by category

²⁸ For each tool, the topic model generates a probability distribution across several potential categories. The tool is then assigned exclusively to the single category that received the highest probability score.

Maintenance activity reflected in tool availability

Our analysis of OSSW on Galaxy shows that active maintenance correlates closely with tool availability on Galaxy instances – a prominent trend across all subdomains. The most popular subdomains (by installations) also demonstrate a strong pattern of frequent updates and active revisions. Notably, there is a strong positive correlation (0.88) between the number of tool revisions and total downloads (typically via installations on Galaxy instances).

“ In our industry, trust and transparency are paramount, and while we share similarities with our competitors, our unique advantage lies in our specialised skillset, customised solutions and active participation in open-source communities that build trust with our customers and the community.” — Interviewee, Ardigen

Trust is earned through consistent maintenance and refinement to meet evolving needs. In essence, we see that there is trust in tools that keep evolving. Regular revisions that enhance or expand functionality, combined with continuous integration systems, appear to foster confidence among Galaxy administrators and the broader community. This likely contributes to higher adoption rates, supporting the growth and impact identified in the independently-commissioned report on the sustainability of Galaxy²⁹.

Key message

Active maintenance fosters trust – and trust drives usage. For example, Sequeone, which provides an end-to-end solution for clinicians and biologists, releases new versions monthly based on customer feedback. It also maintains a dedicated support team and robust security infrastructure, adding value far beyond algorithms. Similarly, another company highlights that clients ‘very much appreciate’ stable software, so much so that they are willing to ‘pay for keeping it stable in the long run’. This underscores the direct link between reliability, ongoing maintenance and user adoption.

Revision count vs. downloads

Revisions and tool downloads correlate in different research categories.

29 Jain, S. (2025). Galaxy Sustainability Report (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16030329>

An analysis of ownership patterns within the Galaxy platform and its tools shows a striking concentration of OSS development. The top ten contributing ToolShed owners are responsible for an impressive 56.6% of the tools in the ToolShed. However, most of these are groups of people, which explains their broad activity

across categories²⁹. This finding shows that small core groups of ToolShed owners play a significant role in sustaining and advancing open source ecosystems³⁰, highlighting the importance of collaborative, long-term maintenance for high-quality tools.

Top ten contributing ToolShed owners in the Galaxy platform

The top ten contributing ToolShed owners in Galaxy are not confined to a single niche; instead, they actively contribute to a wide range of essential domains.

³⁰ Hoffmann, M., Nagle, F., & Zhou, Y. (2024). The Value of Open Source Software. Harvard Business School Strategy Unit Working Paper, (24-038). <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4693148>

Open source sustainability: operationalising collaboration and innovation

OSSW have become integral to the life sciences, underpinning everything from basic research to commercial applications. Organisations of all sizes rely on OSSW to develop products and services. The question is no longer whether to use open source, but how to deploy it strategically to ensure sustainability, security and innovation.

This study demonstrates that industry approaches to OSSW differ based on the extent to which companies align their core products and services with OSSW and integrate community contributions into their business models. Sustainable OSSW adoption requires a combination of open collaboration and robust operational models. Companies that prioritise OSSW and community engagement often see benefits in market growth, talent acquisition and quality improvement. Others integrate OSSW selectively to reduce costs or accelerate development, balancing flexibility with strategic independence. All approaches, however, face common challenges: ongoing maintenance costs, the need to adapt to evolving technologies and appropriate IP protection.

Open source technology, combined with the operational backing of managed services, give development teams significant leverage. This approach allows them to capitalise on mature, widely-adopted open source tools, reducing the burden of foundational development and maintenance. At the same time, the peace of mind offered by managed services frees them to concentrate their energy and resources on building a product."

— Interviewee, Cambrium

Despite heavy reliance on open source tools, modifications are always needed to match specific requirements."

— Interviewee, Saphetor

Finding the balance between the needs of the community and the specific requirements of individual customers, without diverging from the main open source values of the company, can be complicated but is highly feasible."

— Interviewee, Seqera

There is growing recognition that sustainable and secure open science practices are essential. Collaboration remains the most efficient and cost-effective path forward, benefiting all stakeholders, even in commercially-driven environments. Community-driven projects like Nextflow exemplify the power of collective effort in creating robust, open solutions that benefit the research community, regardless of sector.

Challenges around sustainability, scalability and security persist, prompting innovation in both open source adoption and revenue generation. As one Saphetor interviewee noted, *'I want science to be as open as possible for the good of science and society as a whole'*. This statement reflects a broader ethos: open science and specifically, in this case, OSS, is crucial for advancing knowledge and benefiting society.

The examples in this report show it is possible to embed open source into business models, while balancing community benefit with commercial viability. This means investing in active maintenance, adopting common standards and developing governance models that reward both contribution and consumption.

ELIXIR plays a central role in this ecosystem. Through initiatives like the Research Software Ecosystem³¹, a project that centralises high-quality OSSW metadata, ELIXIR members curate and connect metadata for computational biology tools, workflows and libraries, making them more FAIR. Horizon Europe projects^{32,33} led by ELIXIR to promote the adoption and implementation of software best practices³⁴, – particularly for OSSW – and to elevate research software, including OSSW, to a central role in the scientific process. These efforts strengthen reproducibility and trust, reduce duplication and lower integration costs, fueling the growth of OSSW.

For the life sciences community, this is an opportunity to move beyond isolated codebases towards a connected, sustainable knowledge infrastructure. By collaborating across academia, industry and infrastructures, we can ensure open source remains a catalyst for discovery, a driver of efficiency and a foundation for long-term competitiveness. ELIXIR will continue to act as a convenor, standards-setter and enabler in this space, fostering both the openness that accelerates science and the structures that keep it sustainable.

31 <https://research-software-ecosystem.github.io>

32 <https://everse.software/about/objectives>

33 <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/how-funded/eu-projects/steers>

34 <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/how-funded/eu-projects/steers/wp3>

Methods

Computational analysis

The dataset of Galaxy Platform was collected from the Galaxy Tool-shed (26 February 2025) via the Tool-shed API. Due to limited data access, only five metrics were available for analysis: tool name, total downloads, revisions count, unique owners and description. Based on their descriptions, tools were grouped into 15 primary categories using a topic modeling approach. Their primary categories were generated through the modelling process and were not derived from the Galaxy taxonomy.

To assess company engagement and collaboration, 531 public GitHub repositories from 15 interviewed companies were extracted using the GitHub GraphQL API. The analysis compared how companies of different sizes engage with the open source community, focusing on key metrics such as average stars, forks, commits and contributors.

To analyse global collaboration through GitHub, we identified the geographic location of each company, whereas the location of each contributor was extracted from their public GitHub profile. The intensity of collaboration from a specific region was measured by counting the total number of contributors originating from that location.

This study did not differentiate between CI/CD workflows and analytical or ML workflows; we note their different purposes and some shared and distinct features.

All data generated and analysed in this study are publicly available. The complete dataset, including metadata and documentation, is accessible through Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17637118>.

Interview study

From a pool of 678 relevant companies founded between 2014 and 2024, we contacted 258 organisations with accessible founder or management contacts in the health data sector. Fifteen companies agreed to interviews between November 2024 to March 2025. Sessions (30–60 minutes) were held via Zoom or in person at major conferences such as BioTechX 2024 and the Festival of Genomics 2025. Participating companies were categorised by size – small, mid and large – based on their LinkedIn employee counts. In line with EU Recommendation 2003/361, we considered a company as small (less than 50 employees and/or less than €10m EUR turnover), medium (less than 250 employees and/or less than €50m EUR turnover) and large (above these thresholds).

The interviews followed a set of questions that had been developed around workflows and OSS regarding use, active sharing and business-model relevance (value creation, delivery, capture). Responses were analysed based on thematic coding to interpret the data. Interviewees represented their companies throughout, and they reviewed all quoted material. All quotations are used with company consent, and most companies permitted direct attribution. The interviewees that only wanted to share their personal views and experiences preferred to be referenced as anonymous.

We note a sampling bias – most companies had some existing knowledge of ELIXIR, potentially increasing their likelihood of engagement in open source activities. This bias may have influenced our interpretation, particularly regarding the open source ingestion strategy.

While the interviews addressed OSS and workflows, we adopted a flexible approach to the definition of FOSS. This allowed for a wide range of discussions on how companies capture value from OSS without needing to provide it for free.

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